

Clinical Implications of Anatomical Variations of the Facial Nerve in Parotidectomy Patients

Author: Catherine Costan¹

Co-authors: Ruxandra Cojocaru¹, Ana-Isabela Dobrin¹, Anastasia-Parascheva Sandu¹, Sever Stefan Ungureanu¹

Coordinators: Cristina Furnica^{2,1}, Victor-Vlad Costan^{3,1}

Affiliations:

¹ *Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iasi, Romania*

² *Institute of Legal Medicine, Iasi, Romania*

³ *Sf. Spiridon County Clinical Emergency Hospital, Iasi, Romania*

Introduction

Facial surgery is a challenge for the surgeon due to the importance of achieving equally good functional and aesthetic results. One of the most important factors is the predictable distribution of the facial nerve, as any damage to it has significant functional and aesthetic consequences.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on 60 patients undergoing parotidectomy surgery for benign superficial lobe tumors. As the boundary between the superficial and the deep lobes is defined by the facial nerve, this surgery allows for accurate exposure of all its respective branches. Intraoperative photographs were taken before and after the tumor removal.

Results

In 42 patients, 3 distinct branches of the facial nerve were observed, while 4 had 2 branches and 14 had 4 branches. In 49 cases, a singular upper branch followed a trajectory crossing the middle part of the zygomatic arch, while in the other 11 patients we identified 2 different upper branches, an anterior, thinner one and a posterior branch, located in the middle third of the zygomatic arch. In 4 patients, at the most inferior level, the cervicofacial division, we described 2 branches, while the rest had a single branch. 47 patients presented this branch below the basal edge of the mandible, 7 at the same level and 6 above it.

Conclusion

The anatomical landmarks offered by this study, along with the anatomical variations that the surgeon must consider, allow the avoidance of unpleasant situations that could lead to temporary or permanent damage to the facial nerve or any of its branches. One of the most important aspects to keep in mind is being aware of the possibility of a second superior or inferior branch, as damage to either causes lagophthalmos and, respectively, asymmetry of the lower lip, leading to life-altering aesthetic and functional implications.

Keywords

Facial nerve anatomy; Facial surgery; Facial nerve palsy; Parotidectomy